

DESIGN AND BEHAVIOR OF A GRADIENT CFRP BEAM

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SUMMARY: This work examines the advantages that can be gained for laminated flexural composite beams by spatially varying the fiber volume fraction. Design equations are given for a gradient beam whose depth varies while keeping the total fiber content constant. Beam shapes are calculated for a constant surface stress, to reduce the likelihood of failure at the beam root. These solutions are compared to uniform fiber content, all-CFRP beams with the same bending stiffness but with a constant cross-section or a constant surface stress, tapered profile. The gradient beams gave a similar or higher failure load and a lower mass for a given stiffness. The higher resin content also gave an improved vibration damping of the beam. The gradient design leads to a more effective material use. It can be applied to lightweight, dynamically loaded structures such as leaf springs.

KEYWORDS: material gradient, layered beam, cantilever, interlayer, damping, leaf spring, structural optimization

INTRODUCTION

Gradients in composition and properties are a means to improve the performance of structural components. While one may want to apply a material with a desired property or functionality locally while making the rest of the structure of different materials, the interface between dissimilar material leads to processing stresses and stress concentrations during loading. A gradient in properties helps to reduce these stresses and thus to improve the performance of material or part. On a broader level, parts may be designed with material gradients in order to control the overall distribution of stresses. Functionally gradient materials (FGMs) are thus a means to optimize the use of materials and increase reliability.

Current FGM research is focused in particular on metal and ceramic matrix composites [1]. However, polymer composites and related materials with a gradient in properties have been the subject of very few studies to this date [2, 3]. A major practical difficulty is to produce the desired compositional and microstructural gradient [2]. The aim of the present work is to investigate the design and behavior of gradient CFRP cantilever beam with a gradient in effective fiber volume fraction along its length (Fig. 1). Unlike all-composite beams with a uniform fiber content and a tapered profile, this solution avoids the problem of stress concentrations and delamination-related failures common with laminate designs using ply drops [4]. The design objective is a constant stress at the beam surface, in order to improve the strength or reduce the mass of the beam for a given stiffness, and thus improve the effectiveness of material use.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of a CFRP cantilever beam with a gradient in fiber content.

BEAM DESIGN

The beam under study is shown in Figure 2. It is shown as a cantilever, but could also represent half of a simply supported 3-point bending beam. The beam is taken as a unidirectional composite with a fiber orientation corresponding to the beam's longitudinal axis. The total fiber content is constant over the entire length of the beam, while the effective fiber volume fraction changes with the depth of the beam. The beam, of total length L , has a tip length a of constant thickness y_0 and fiber volume fraction, ϕ_0 . For $x \leq a$, the cross section is constant, and a force P applied to the beam tip leads to linearly increasing surface strains. In the rest of the beam, the depth $y(x)$ increases gradually while the fiber volume fraction $\phi(x)$ decreases. The fiber volume fraction is given by:

$$\phi(x) = A_f / y(x)b(x) \quad (1)$$

where $b(x)$ is the beam's width and the total fiber area A_f is constant along the beam's length.

Fig. 2: Definition of the geometry of the cantilever beam

Fig. 3: Ideal (left) and layered (right) gradient beam cross sections. Fibers are represented by black dots.

Two cases are considered: an ideal gradient composite beam in which the fibers are distributed evenly within a cross-section across the beam's thickness at any point along its length, and a laminated beam, in which resin layers are introduced between composite layers (Fig. 3).

In the case of an ideal gradient beam with fibers distributed uniformly in a cross-section, the composite's longitudinal modulus is:

$$E(x) = (\phi(x)R + (1 - \phi(x)))E_m \quad (2)$$

where $R = E_f/E_m$ is the ratio of fiber to matrix modulus. The bending stiffness of any section along the length of a beam of constant width is:

$$(EI)_{eq}(x) = \frac{E_m y^2(x)}{12} (A_f(R-1) + y(x)b) \quad (3)$$

The surface stress for $x \geq a$ is given by equilibrium:

$$\sigma_{surf}(x) = \frac{My(x)}{2I(x)} = \frac{6Px}{y^2(x)} = const. \quad (4)$$

The beam profile for a criterion of constant surface stress σ^* at the beam's surface is thus:

$$y = \sqrt{6Sx} \quad \text{where } S = P/\sigma^* \quad (5)$$

For $x \geq a$, the surface strain is:

$$\epsilon_{surf}(x) = \frac{My(x)}{2(EI)_{eq}(x)} = \frac{6Px}{(A_f(R-1) + y(x)b)E_m y(x)} = const. \quad (6)$$

Setting this strain constant, ϵ^* , for $x \geq a$, gives a quadratic equation that can be solved for y :

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \left(-B + \sqrt{B^2 - 4C} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $B = (R-1)\phi_o y_o$ and $C = -6Tx/E_m$, $T = \frac{P}{\epsilon^*} = \frac{2E_o I_o}{ay_o} = \frac{E_o y_o^2}{6a}$ (8)

where E_o and I_o are the modulus and moment of inertia of the composite beam for $x \leq a$. The deflection of the beam is calculated by the method of complementary virtual work:

$$\delta = \int_0^L \frac{M(x)}{(EI)_{eq}(x)} M_v(x) dx$$
 (9)

Giving the compliance:

$$\frac{\delta}{P} = \int_0^a \frac{12x^2}{(B+y_o)y_o^2 E_m} dx + \int_a^L \frac{12x^2}{(B+y)y^2 E_m} dx = \frac{a^3}{3E_o I_o} + \int_a^L \frac{12x^2}{(B+y)y^2 E_m} dx$$
 (10)

or, simplifying,
$$\frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{2a^2}{3Ty_o} + \int_a^L \frac{4x}{T(\sqrt{B+24Tx/E_m} - B)} dx$$
 (11)

The deformation due to shear is negligible for long beams as examined here. For continuity, the surface stress or strain for $x \geq a$ is set equal to the stress or strain at $x=a$,

$$\sigma^* = \frac{P a y_o}{I_o} \text{ OR } \epsilon^* = \frac{P a y_o}{2E_o I_o}$$
 (12)

From Eqn (5) for constant stress or (7) and (8) for constant strain, and Eqn (11), the thickness y_o and the profile $y(x)$ of the tapered part of the beam can be calculated iteratively for a beam tip of given length a , modulus E_o , fiber volume fraction ϕ_o , and a desired compliance. The profiles of beams with a constant section tip $a=0.2L$ are given for different ratios $R = E_f/E_m$ in Fig. 4. The lowest curve gives the profile of a homogenous beam with constant surface stress. The upper curve, for $E_f/E_m = 500$ is practically the limiting profile for very high fiber-to-matrix moduli ratios. Increasing the ratio to 10000 would change the calculated maximum thickness by less than one percent.

Fig. 4: Beam profiles for constant surface stress or strain. The ratio of fiber to matrix modulus is indicated on the graph.

In the second case, the gradient beam is analyzed by simple beam theory for layered beams. The beam's length is divided into segments of constant sectional properties:

$$(EI)_{eq}^j = \sum_i E_i b \left[(t_i^j)^3 / 12 + t_i^j (\bar{y}_i^j)^2 \right] \quad (13)$$

where t_i^j is thickness and \bar{y}_i^j the distance from the beam's neutral plane of layer i in segment j . For given layer properties, the thickness of the layers in each segment are calculated iteratively to obtain a constant surface stress along the beam's length and a desired flexural compliance, calculated by Eqn (11).

EXPERIMENTAL

The cantilever beams tested in the present study were made of a unidirectional pitch-based CFRP prepreg (Nippon Steel Corporation, Japan), and an epoxy adhesive film (Toho Cytec, Japan). The processed CFRP prepreg had a thickness of about 0.18 ± 0.02 mm, a longitudinal modulus of 200 GPa, and a relative density of 1.64. Its strength, measured from bending tests, was 965 MPa. The epoxy film contained an approximately 10% volume fraction of woven glass fiber carrier fabric. Its average thickness was 0.075 mm, with an in-plane modulus of 8 GPa and a relative density of 1.35.

Various beam geometries, described in Table 1 and Fig. 5, were investigated. The effective fiber volume fraction in a cross-section was varied along the beam's length by inserting the adhesive film between the prepregs. The adhesive film layers were evenly distributed between the prepreg plies through the thickness of the beam. Short beam samples of constant thickness, with one layer of epoxy film at their midplane were tested in three-point bending with a span to depth ratio of 10 to determine the strength of the bond between the prepregs and adhesive film. As none of the samples failed in the adhesive or the interface, the bond was considered to be strong enough not to form a detrimentally weak plane. Finally, samples with varying thicknesses, and in particular samples designed for constant surface stress or strain, were tested and compared to the values for constant cross-section, all-CFRP beams.

Table 1: Sample description

Sample ID	Description
C	Only CFRP
I	Constant thickness CFRP, 0.075mm interlayer at mid-plane
G2	Layered beam, reduced surface stress
G3	Layered beam, constant surface stress (& strain)

The composite was laid up by hand in 125mm x 250mm plates with the fiber direction along the long axis of the plate. It was then cured in an autoclave at 140°C and 5 bar for 60min, with a heating rate of 2°C/min and slow cooling. As the plates were cured on a flat plate half-tool, they had one flat and one convex face. The cured plates were cut into 15mm wide beams with the fibers parallel to the long axis of the beam. Half beams were used for the cantilever tests, with a clamping length of 15mm, while three-point bending tests were conducted on the whole beam. The final fiber distribution through the thickness of the beams was determined from optical micrographs of the polished beam edges. The measured values were then used to back-calculate the processed beam's stiffness and stresses using the multilayered beam model.

Fig. 5: Profile of multilayered gradient beams G2 and G3. The profiles of ideal gradient beams for constant surface stress or strain are also shown.

The gradient beams were tested statically as a cantilever and in three-point bending. The bending stiffness, the load at first damage, the maximum load, and the residual bearing capacity after failure were obtained from quasistatic tests on an Instron load frame, at a tip deflection rate of 2mm/min. The quasistatic test were run with the flat face on the compression, as well as on the tension side of the beam. The load-deflection curve was recorded for all tests, and the strain was measured at five points on the G3 gradient beam using strain gauges.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Cantilever test results for the G2 and G3 beams, L=100mm. Calculated values, in parentheses, are given for constant cross section and constant surface stress all-CFRP beams having the same stiffnesses as the gradient beams.

Beam ID	Thickness [mm]	Mass M [g]	P / δ [N/mm]	(P/δ)/M [N/mm/g]	P _{max} [N]
G2	2.85 / 1.13 *	4.12	5.24 (5.38)	1.27	56 (99)
Const section	(1.91)	(4.70)	5.24	(1.11)	(88)
Const surf. stress	(2.37 / 1.06) *	(4.06)	5.24	(1.29)	(68)
G3	4.20 / 1.13 *	4.78	10.1 (9.09)	2.11	91 (149)
Const section	(2.38)	(5.85)	10.1	(1.73)	(137)
Const surf. stress	(2.95 / 1.32) *	(5.06)	10.1	(2.00)	(105)

*Max / min thickness

The bending stiffness and maximum load capacity of the gradient beams loaded as cantilevers with a length of 100mm are reported in Table 2. They are compared to the calculated values for all-CFRP beams with the same bending stiffness but a uniform fiber content and of constant cross-section or designed for a constant surface stress. The bending stiffness of the beams is also given normalized by the mass of the beams. The expected maximum load was calculated based on the measured bending strength of the CFRP (965MPa) and the maximum stress at the beam's surface. Both gradient beams have the lowest or close to the lowest mass, and the highest strength per unit mass for a given stiffness. For a stiffness-based design, they thus represent a more weight-effective solution, and further use less carbon fiber

reinforcement fiber. The constant-section beam, although it has a slightly higher expected strength than the all-CFRP beam with a constant surface stress, has a significantly higher mass.

The results of the instrumented cantilever test for beam G3, with five strain gauges on both the compression and tension sides of the beam, are given in Fig. 6. The graph shows the calculated and measured axial stress as a function of position along the surface of beam. As the surface layer consisted of CFRP throughout, this also corresponds to the strain distribution. The measured stresses correspond adequately to the calculated values. Also shown is the linear stress distribution expected for a constant section beam with the same bending stiffness. The maximum stress in the latter is slightly higher than for the gradient beam, and the strength, assuming tensile failure of the surface CFRP layer, is thus correspondingly lower (Table 2).

Fig. 6: Strain as a function of position at the surface of gradient beam G3.

Table 3: Three-point bending test results, $L=190\text{mm}$. Calculated values, in parentheses, are given for constant section and constant surface stress all-CFRP beams with the same stiffness.

Beam ID	Thickness [mm]	Mass M [g]	P / δ [N/mm]	$(P / \delta) / M$ [N/mm/g]	P_{\max} [N]
G2	2.85/1.13 *	9.02	15.15 (15.63)	1.68	160 (214)
Const section	(2.05)	(9.58)	15.15	(1.58)	(213)
G3	4.20/1.13 *	11.16	28.57 (30.30)	2.56	235 (334)
Const section	(2.54)	(11.86)	28.57	(2.41)	(328)

*Max / min thickness

The bending stiffness and maximum load capacity of the gradient beams loaded in three-point bending with a span of 190mm are reported in Table 3. They are compared to the calculated values for beams of same stiffness but with a constant fiber content and cross-section. In this test configuration, the gradient beams did not have the constant section tip like the cantilever. As the design for constant surface stress holds only for a given tip length a , the G3 beam does not have a constant surface stress for this test geometry. However, in this case as well, the gradient beams have a lower mass and equivalent predicted strength for a given beam stiffness.

Fig. 7: Force-deflection curves for gradient beam samples G2 and G3 under 3-point bending, span=190mm.

Fig. 8: Fracture through the thickness of gradient beam G3, three-point bending test. The load application point is slightly left of the failed area. The dark layers are the CFRP lamina, the light ones are the adhesive film.

Constant-section CFRP beams, tested in three-point bending at various spans ranging from 16mm to 100mm, all collapsed suddenly as a result of tensile failure of the CFRP at mid-span. The gradient beams, on the other hand, had a more gradual failure (Fig. 7). For beam G2, a more or less simultaneous damage of the resin layers and tensile failure of the CFRP were observed, although the former very likely preceded the latter. On the other hand, the first evidence of damage was clearly observed in the resin layers in beam G3. This damage developed in steps through successive layers (Fig. 8), starting with the topmost, compressively stressed layer. This was followed, after extensive damage leading to a reduction of the bending stiffness, to a tensile failure of the CFRP and final collapse of the beam. As the damage leading to failure started in the resin layers, the gradient beams did not reach the maximum expected load calculated on the assumption of a tensile failure of the CFRP. The ductility of the gradient beams was calculated as the area under the load-deflection curve from the initial failure to collapse divided by the area before failure, and is

expressed in percent in Table 4. It is highest for the G3 beam, which has the highest resin content in the highly stressed zones close to the surface of the beam.

Table 4: Post-failure behavior, three-point bending test results, $L=190\text{mm}$. Calculated values are given for a constant cross section all-CFRP beams having the same stiffnesses as the gradient beams.

Beam ID	P_{\max} [N]	Residual load [N]	Res. load [% P_{\max}]	Ductility [%]
G2	160	103	64%	20
Const section	(213)	--		< 10
G3	235	193	82%	58
Const section	(328)	--		< 10

Introducing layers of epoxy increased the damping of the beams, even for the constant thickness, all-CFRP beam with a single 0.075mm layer at the midplane. This results from the higher damping of the epoxy film compared to the CFRP. The first mode loss coefficient of the gradient beams, which contained a much larger proportion of epoxy interlayers, was five to six times higher than that of the all-CFRP beams. This agrees with previous findings [5, 6] that improved damping is obtained through the use of low-stiffness interlayers in CFRP.

Table 5: Vibration frequencies and damping of gradient and constant cross section all-CFRP cantilevers, $L=100\text{mm}$. Calculated values in parentheses are obtained by Raleigh's method.

Beam ID	1st mode freqs [Hz]	1st mode loss factor[%]
C	196 (230)	0.18
I	176 (216)	0.20
G2	338 (466)	1.13
Const section	(341)	--
G3	499 (646)	0.90
Const section	(425)	--

Overall, the static and dynamic performance of CFRP beams is improved by the use of a material gradient. By adapting the stiffness of the beam to the load by increasing the content of lower density and lower cost resin, a beam of a desired stiffness is made lighter and with an equivalent strength using a smaller amount of composite prepreg. Furthermore, as the material distribution in the beam is changed gradually, there are no deleterious stress concentrations that could lead to failures related to delaminations, as is the case with ply drops in all-composite beams. The next step is to improve the performance of the beams investigated here by achieving a true material gradient without property jump at the CFRP/resin layer interface.

CONCLUSIONS

The design and behavior of gradient CFRP flexural beams have been investigated. The design equations are presented for an ideal gradient beam, with a uniform fiber distribution in cross-sections along the length, and for a layered beam. The latter is a practical approximation to a true gradient beam, and was produced and tested in this work. This type of beam has demonstrated good performance in terms of low mass and equivalent strength for a given bending stiffness. The gradient beam designed for constant surface stress weighed less than all-composite beams with the same stiffness and had the highest bending stiffness and strength per unit of mass of all beams examined. It failed in a more ductile manner than

the constant-section CFRP beams, and had an improved vibration damping. The behavior of the gradient beams is predicted accurately by the multilayered beam model.

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